

PEDAGOGIK FAOLIYATDA RIVOJLANISH-PEDAGOGIK QOBILIYATLARDAN FOYDALANISH ASOSI

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Annotatsiya. mazkur maqolada pedagoglar, pedagogik faoliyat turlari haqida, pedagogikaga hissa qo`shgan olimlarning qarashlari, pedagogik muammolar, innovatsion g`oyalar bilan sug`orilgan fanlarni o`qitish hozirgi zamon talabiga aylanayotgani va fanlarni o`qitishda yingilik kiritish masalalari tavsiflangan.

Kalit so`zlar: Pedagog, pedagogik faoliyat turlari, pedagogika tarixi va kelajagi, kreativ ,raqobatbardosh kadr, tashabbus ko`rsatish, kommunikativ faoliyat.

THE BASIS OF THE USE OF DEVELOPMENT-PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS IN PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY

Abstract. This article describes pedagogues, types of pedagogical activities, the views of scientists who contributed to pedagogy, pedagogical problems, the fact that the teaching of subjects with innovative ideas is becoming a requirement of the present time, and the issues of innovation in the teaching of subjects.

Key words: Pedagogue, types of pedagogical activity, history and future of pedagogy, creative, competitive staff, initiative, communicative activity.

ОСНОВЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ РАЗВИВАЮЩЕ-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ УМЕНИЙ В ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

Аннотация. В статье говорится, что необходимость обеспечения образования, основанного на новых идеях, новых идеях и инновациях, является наиболее актуальной задачей современности, что преподавание предметов с инновационными идеями становится требованием настоящего времени, а внедрение инноваций в преподавание предметов, описаны вопросы эффективного использования зарубежного опыта.

Ключевые слова: Педагог, виды педагогической деятельности, история и будущее педагогики, творческий, конкурентоспособный коллектив, инициатива, коммуникативная активность.

Pedagogika nima ? U nimani o`rganadi, nima bilan shug`ullanadi, nimani tadqiq qiladi?, degan savollar pedagogika fanini o`rganishga kirishgan insonni aqlini band qiladi. Pedagogika - tarbiya haqidagi fan, pedagogika o`lib kelayotgan yosh avlodni tarbiyalash haqidagi fan.

Pedagogika qadimdan ma`lum bo`lgan, yunoncha “bola yetaklovchi” degan ma`noni anglatadi. Pedagogika tarbiya haqidagi fan sifatida tarbiyani mohiyatini tushinishi , uning qonuniyatlarini ochishi ,shu orqali inson manfaatlari uchun tarbiya jarayoniga ta`sir etishni nazarda tutadi . Pedagogika jamiyatni rivojlanish qonun qoidalariga tayangan holda taraqqiy etadi. Pedagogik faoliyat bu - yosh avlodni iqtisodiy, siyosiy, axloqiy, estetik maqsadlarga muvofiq ravishda ongli hayotga tayyorlashga qaratilgan. Pedagogik jarayonda pedagogik faoliyat turlari: o`quv va tarbiyaviy ishlardir.

Tarbiyaviy ish bu- insonlarning komil inson bo`lib yetishishi , har xil muammolarni hal eta olishi , shaxslarni turli faoliyat turlarini boshqarishga qaratiladi. Tarbiyaviy ishda -bola ruhiyatidan kelib chiqqan holda ish ko`riladi . Ta`lim sohasini asosiy maqsadi - ta`lim samaradorligiga erishishga qo`yilgan maqsadga erishishni ko`zda tutadi . “Ilm boylikdan afzal , chunki ilm seni asraydi, boylikni esa sen asraysan” . Xalqimizda bejiz bu jumlar keltirilmagan . Pedagogik taraqqiyotning samarali bo`lishi o`qituvchidan quyidagi qobiliyat turlarini talab qiladi:

1)Perseptiv 5) Diqqatni to`g`ri taqsimlay olish 6)Tashkilotchilik 7)Konsruktiv .
8)Kommunikativ .

Tashabbuskor va g`ayratli o`qituvchi bolalarni o`z orqasidan ergashtira oladi . Bolalarni kelajagi bilimi ularni vatanga sodiq fuqaro qilib tarbiyalashga safarbar qila oladigan insongina haqiqiy o`qituvchi bo`la oladi. Bolaga befarq, uning kelajagi bilan qiziqmaydigan , o`qituvchilik kasbiga loqayd inson haqiqiy o`qituvchi bo`la olmaydi.

O`qituvchining kasbiy - ma`naviy axloqiy sifatlari: Pedagogik mahoratni oshirib , kelajakka bo`lgan ishonch , ijogkorlik , kasbiy pedagogik fikrlash , nutq texnikasiga egalik , pedagogik texnikadan samarali foydalanish , o`quvchi fikrini tinglash, tartib-intizom , tashkilotchilik, fanni oxirgi yutuqlaridan xabardorlik.

Sharq uyg`onish davrida ilm o`chog`I Bag`dod shahri edi . Bag`dodda “Bayt ul -hikma”- “Donishmandlar uyi” tashkil etilgan. Bu ilm maskanida o`zimizning buyuk allomalarimiz Ahmad Al Farg`oniy , Xorazmiy , Forobiy faoliyat yuritishgan .

Forobiy -Sharqda “Sharq Arastusi”, “Ikkinchi Muallim” nomlari bilan ulug`langan. Forobiy o`rta asr davri ta`biy ilmiy va ijtimoiy bilimlar sohasida asarlar yaratgan .

Abu Ali Ibn Sino Axloq va ta`lim tarbiya borasida shunday deydi: “ Yaxshi, yomon xalqning hammasi sharoit , tarbiya odatlanish natijasida vujudga keladi . Ilm - narsalarning inson aqli yordamida o`rganilishidir”. Ibn Sino o`quvchilar o`rtasida raqobatdoshlik guruh bahslari, munozaralarini foydaliligini, o`quvchilarni birgalikda, jamoada o`qitishni afzalliklari haqida aytib o`tgan.

O`zbekistonimizda bugungi zamonaviy muhitda faoliyat yuritib kelayotgan pedagoglarni axborot texnologiyalari sohasida bilimlarni yetishmasligi, zamonaviy texnologiyalardan dars jarayonida qo`llamasligi , ta`limning sifat darajasini tushishiga olib kelmoqda . Hozirda oliy ilmiy pedagoglarning tajribalari , dars o`tish qobiliyati , zo`r bo`lishidan tashqari, ular dars jarayonlarini qiziqarli innavatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanib , innavatsion ko`rgazmali qurollardan foydalanmasdan darsni sifat darajasi pasayishi mumkin deb o`ylayman .

Chunki asrimiz bolalariga eski dars usulida dars o`tish ularni qiziqtirish qiyin, har bir pedagog o`z ustida ko`p ishlashi, dars jarayonlariga chuqur tayyorgarlik ko`rishi , bilimlarni o`rganib, fanga tadbiq qila olishlari kerak, shundagina davlatimizda ta`lim sifati yaxshilanib , yaxshi pedagoglar yetishib chiqadi.

Endilikda oliy ta`limdagi mavjud talabalarni faqat tayyor bilimlarni egallashga o`rgatish bilan kutilgan natijaga erishib bo`lmaydi. Bunday usul talabalarda mustaqil fikrlash, ijodiy izlanish, tashabbus ko`rsatish qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga imkon bermaydi. Shuning uchun ham yangi fikr, yangi g`oya, innovatsiyaga tayangan holda ta`lim berish ehtiyoji bugungi kunning eng dolzarb vazifasiga aylandi.

Har bir darsda yangi g`oya, innovatsion texnologiyani qo`llash uchun talabalar oldindan izlanishi, ilg`or tajribalarni o`rganishi va o`zi ishlab chiqqan hamda samarali natijadorlikka ega bo`lgan usullarni qo`llay olishi zarur.

O`zbekiston xalq ta`limi tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasida va “Ta`lim to`g`risida”gi Qonun loyihasi (Yangi tahriri) da ham innovatsion ta`limni rivojlantirishga katta e`tibor qaratilgan. O`zbekiston Respublikasi “Ta`lim to`g`risida” gi Qonun loyihasi (yangi tahriri) ning 5- moddasida: “...Ta`lim tashkilotlarida innovatsion faoliyat va ta`lim dasturlarini innovatsion texnologiyalari yordamida amalga oshirishni qo`llab-quvvatash” ko`rsatilgan.

Ko`rinib turibdiki, innvatsion ta`lim berish bugungi kunda talabalarning asosiy faoliyat turi bo`lib, o`qituvchilarning bu boradagi tajribasini o`rganish va targ`ib qilish ham ta`lim sifati hamda samaradorligini oshirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb eadi. Zero, innovatsion ta`lim-buyuk kelajak poydevori bo`lib, uni o`rganish va o`rgatish oliy ta`lim o`qituvchilari oldida turgan dolzarb vazifadir.

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